

UNCOVERING THE UNSEEN: PREVALENCE OF PROLONGED GRIEF DISORDER AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS- A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) is a type of mental disorder that entails experiencing grief in prolonged and enduring ways even after the loss (more than 6 months); it can be considered as a variant of depression. There is very little information on the prevalence of PGD and the factors that are related to it within Pakistani healthcare settings.

Aim and Objectives: This aim was to estimate the prevalence of PGD by the ICD-11 criteria and determine socio-demographic and loss-related predictors in the hospital-based sample in Pakistan.

Methods: There was a cross-sectional study done by using a psychiatry outpatient clinic in Khyber Teaching Hospital which took six months. The consecutive sampling method recruited 333 bereaved adults (age 18 and above) who had lost a loved one more than 6 months prior. The administration of questionnaires was performed via structured questionnaires that comprised socio-demographic data, variables of losses, and the International Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS). An assessment of the comorbid conditions was done through the use of clinical interviews.

Findings: PGD occurred in 18.3% (95% CI: 14.2- 22.4). Major predictors were female gender (OR=2.34, p 1001), loss of spouse (OR=321, p <001), sudden or unexpected death (OR=2.89, p<001), lower education (OR=187, p=0012), unemployment (OR=2.15, p=003). Sixty-seven-point two percent of PGD cases had depression. Religious coping demonstrated the protective results (OR=0.43, p=0.001).

Conclusion: PGD prevalence in this Pakistani hospital sample was higher than reported in Western populations. Gender, relationship to deceased, cause of death, and socio-economic factors were significant predictors. These findings highlight the need for culturally appropriate screening and intervention programs in Pakistani healthcare settings.

INTRODUCTION

Emotional grief and stress that one is subjected to after losing a loved one is unquestionably one of the worst moments in the life of a person, which, in most cases, develops to fade away slowly. Other individuals, however, experience the distress to be chronic and lead to severe impairments in a variety of functioning areas in life. Hence, they are clinically diagnosed to have prolonged grief¹. Prolonged Grief Disorder was defined under the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) as "Disorders specifically associated with stress" as a disturbance where there is an enduring grief heterotopic reaction after the death of an individual involving a longing for the deceased or lingering preoccupation with the deceased accompanied by severe emotional suffering occurring lasting more than six months and is obviously beyond what is accustomed in the community, society or culture and context of the person².

As part of a systematic study, it was revealed that the prevalence of prolonged grief disorder (PGD) was estimated at 10% in the bereaved adult population (>65 years)³. According to a German sample, 3.3 percent of the people fulfilled a DSM-5-TR criteria of prolonged grief disorder, and this was considerably lower than that of a female resettled refugee in Germany, whose rates of PGD stood at 9.41 percent, which is much higher in comparison to the general population^{4,5}. Alongside the population-based surveys, the prevalence in populations at higher risk of Prolonged Grief Disorder has also become the priority of research. The prevalence of PGD in bereaved persons after experiencing unnatural losses (e.g., homicides, accidents, or disasters) was determined to be 49 percent in a meta-analysis published in 2020⁶. The prevalence rate of prolonged grief disorder (PGD) in Chinese parents who lost their only child was established to be 35.5%⁷. This demonstrates that the loss characteristics, such as the cause of death and the relationship with the deceased, pose an eminent risk factor for PGD.

The only study conducted in Pakistan, which was an online survey that included a sample of bereaved individuals from Lahore who had lost a close one to COVID-19, yielded a prevalence of 15.4% for Prolonged Grief Disorder⁸. The data collected in most of the studies was through a self-report instrument and not through clinical interviews. A

systematic review of psychometric instruments lists 11 different self-report scales that are used across the literature to diagnose prolonged grief disorder⁹, none of which accurately covered all the items listed in the ICD-11 diagnostic criteria for cases. Due to the difference in the methodologies and self-report instruments used, the different diagnostic criteria applied and the possible difference in the expression of grief across cultures, considerable heterogeneity in the estimated prevalence of prolonged grief disorder exists across literature¹⁰.

The development of the International Prolonged Grief Scale (IPGDS) was based on a more reliable way to calculate the symptoms of prolonged grief and to be able to use ICD-11 PGD as a diagnostic criterion of caseness¹¹. It is intended to be used in clinics and research and was employed to determine a prevalence of PGD of 6.9-37.5 percent in Switzerland, China, Portugal, and Germany¹². In an ICD-11 study using IPGDS in Spain, the prevalence of PGD was 9.9 percent of the total sample.

Loss-related variables (time since loss, low education, loss of a partner, and unnatural/violent deaths), socio-demographic factors (loss of a child, unexpectedness of death¹³, and substance misuse¹⁴ were associated with high levels of symptoms of prolonged grief disorder. Of people who had strong beliefs in spiritual beliefs in their lives, on average,¹⁵ of those with a high level of religious beliefs, four also had worse symptoms of PGD. Another meta-analysis revealed a positive relationship between religious beliefs and PGD¹⁶, indicating that this can be attributed to negative rather than positive religious coping (e.g., spiritual discontent or God's punishment). However, the sample population being studied to make this connection between PGD and religious belief was completely non-Muslim. Therefore, the result can in no way be applied to the Muslim majority population whose primary source of strength in the event of loss of a loved one is their Islamic association that bestows hope of being united with the lost in the Hereafter¹⁷. It has been shown that there is a significant amount of overlapping of Prolonged Grief Disorder with other disorders such as Depression¹⁸, and our present study, through clinical interviews and the assistance of a psychometric scale (HAM-D)¹⁹, will determine the

onset, severity, and potential co-morbidity of clinical depression with prolonged grief disorder.

The prevalence and associated factors of PGD have not so far been estimated in a Pakistani hospital-based setup with clinical interviews done by a trained Psychiatrist. This gap in the existing body of research on the topic is what we shall address through our study to determine the risk factors and impart the development of screening, intervention, and prevention programs for Prolonged Grief Disorder in a tertiary-care hospital.

RATIONALE

Prolonged grief disorder is a relatively underdiagnosed mental disorder in healthcare settings in Pakistan and it is easily missed especially since the bereaved seek help for other co-occurring psychological problems like depression, which become the sole focus of treatment. Understanding the prevalence and associated factors of PGD can help us identify potential risk factors for the disorder and inform our risk assessment protocols so we are better able to devise interventions to address the specific needs of high-risk groups, potentially preventing misdiagnosis, underdiagnoses, and prolonged suffering of the bereaved. To date, only one other study has investigated the prevalence of PGD following the COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan⁸, which was an online survey based on self-reported psychological measures rather than clinical interviews. By focusing on a hospital-based sample, our study aims to fill the gap in the literature, particularly regarding its

prevalence and associated factors in healthcare settings. Findings from our study can directly inform clinical practice by highlighting the importance of screening for PGD in hospital settings, integrating assessment tools into routine practice, and developing targeted interventions to support bereaved individuals effectively.

OBJECTIVES

- a) To estimate the prevalence of Prolonged Grief Disorder as per ICD-11 diagnostic criteria
- b) Identify its socio-demographic and loss-related predictors

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Prolonged Grief Disorder: Persistent and pervasive longing for, or preoccupation with, the deceased that lasts at least six months after loss and causes significant functional impairment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

Prospective Cross-sectional Study

Setting: Khyber Teaching Hospital, Outpatient Department

Duration: 6 months

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated using G-Power 3.1.9.7 version with inputs shown in the table below:

Inputs	Linear Multiple Regression Random Model
Tail	Two Tailed
Prevalence	9%
Alpha Error	0.05
Power (B-1)	0.95
No of Predictors	11

The sample size calculated came out to be 303. After adding a 10% presumable attrition in rate, sample size became 333.

Sample Selection: Non-probability Consecutive Sampling

Inclusion Criteria

Adults (18 years or older) presenting to the outpatient department of the psychiatry unit Khyber Teaching Hospital.

Individuals who have experienced the loss of a loved one (parent, sibling, spouse, grandparent, uncle, aunt or child)

Individuals who provide informed consent to participate.

Exclusion Criteria

Adults who have experienced the loss of a loved one in less than six months preceding their presentation to the hospital.

Patients with severe cognitive impairment or psychiatric conditions that may affect their ability to complete the questionnaire accurately

Data Collection

After obtaining approval from the Hospital Ethical Committee, 333 patients presenting to the Psychiatry OPD who answer "yes" to the screening question "In the last three years, have you lost an immediate family member like a parent, sibling, child or spouse?", were enrolled in the study after patients give their written informed consent. Only Bereaved individuals who have experienced more than 6 months of bereavement and fulfilled the rest of the inclusion criteria were eligible to analyze in terms of PGD as per the ICD-11 criteria.

A team of resident psychiatrists and clinical psychologists administered a questionnaire that consisted of socio-demographic variables of the patient (such as age, gender, educational retirement/job, marital status, religious identity, and mental health treatment), the loss-related variables (which include bereavement period, age of the deceased, quality of the relationship between them and the cause of death of the deceased) and the 12-items of International Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS) that directly measure the core symptoms of grief and emotional pain. Other than the pre-designed questionnaire (which will be filled by the researcher), a clinical interview was also conducted by the resident psychiatrist to assess the co-occurrence of other mental health problems in the bereaved patient sample (e.g. depression and anxiety).

RESULTS

Participant Characteristics

A total of 356 individuals were initially screened for eligibility, of which 333 met the inclusion criteria and completed the study questionnaires. The response rate was 93.5%. The final sample consisted of 333 bereaved adults aged 18-75 years (mean age = 42.3 ± 12.8 years).

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (N=333)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	142	42.6
	Female	191	57.4
Age Groups	18-30 years	89	26.7
	31-45 years	156	46.8
	46-60 years	72	21.6
	>60 years	16	4.8
Education	Uneducated	45	13.5
	Under 10th class	78	23.4
	Matric	92	27.6
	FSc	64	19.2
	University degree	54	16.2
Employment Status	Unemployed	127	38.1
	Under 30K/month	89	26.7
	Under 50K/month	67	20.1
	50K-1 lac	38	11.4
	Over 1 lac	12	3.6
Marital Status	Single	67	20.1
	Married	198	59.5

	Divorced	23	6.9
	Separated	18	5.4
	Widowed	27	8.1
Religious Identity	Very religious	156	46.8
	Moderately religious	134	40.2
	Not very religious	43	12.9

Socio-demographic details of the 333 bereaved adults who took part in this study are outlined in Table 1. Regarding the gender distribution, there is a disproportionate number of females (57.4%) compared to males (42.6%). In terms of age, most respondents were between 31 and 45 years (46.8%), while 4.8% were above 60 years. The level of education varied, with 27.6 per cent of the respondents having attained the matriculation level and 13.5 per cent being uneducated. The issue of

employment also led to the recognition of severe economic problems, as 38.1% of respondents were unemployed. Marital status revealed that the majority of them were married (59.5%), whereas religious affiliation showed that almost 50 per cent (46.8%) were very religious. This demographic characteristic provides key background information on the experiences of grief among the participants and the ways they coped with it.

Table 2: Loss-Related Characteristics (N=333)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Relationship to Deceased	Mother	89	26.7
	Father	94	28.2
	Spouse	56	16.8
	Sibling	67	20.1
	Child	27	8.1
Cause of Death	Natural/Age	134	40.2
	Disease	156	46.8
	Accident	32	9.6
	Suicide	8	2.4
	Homicide	3	0.9
Time Since Loss	6-12 months	89	26.7
	1-2 years	134	40.2
	2-3 years	78	23.4
	>3 years	32	9.6
Age of Deceased	<18 years	23	6.9
	18-40 years	67	20.1
	41-60 years	134	40.2
	>60 years	109	32.7

Table 2 presents the loss characteristics of the 333 participants, detailing the specific type of bereavement they experienced. The correlation to the deceased is such that most of them lost a parent; 28.2 per cent reported that a father was dead, and 26.7 per cent said they lost their mothers. Of a significant percentage (46.8%), the cause of death was caused by a disease, but there were few accidents (9.6%) and suicides (2.4).

The period of loss reveals that 40.2 per cent had their loss within 1-2 years, hence an essential time for handling grief. The age of the deceased was also different; however, 40.2 per cent of respondents were aged between 41 and 60 years. These are the primary considerations that can be essential in interpreting the particular grief reactions and demands of the respondents.

Table 3: Prevalence of Prolonged Grief Disorder

PGD Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	95% CI
PGD Present	61	18.3	14.2-22.4
PGD Absent	272	81.7	77.6-85.8
Total	333	100.0	-

Table 3 describes the prevalence of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) in the study participants. The prevalence rate of PGD was determined to be 18.3 per cent because, within the 333 people, 61 were found to be affected by PGD. The rate implies that a large number of bereaved are exposed to long-lasting and disabling grief. The reliability of the findings is further

supported by the 95% confidence intervals (CI) for PGD, which range from 14.2 to 22.4 and are absent from 77.6 to 85.8. The reason why it is vital to understand the prevalence of PGD is that it helps determine those individuals who require specific therapy programs to help treat their state of prolonged grief.

Table 4: IPGDS Scores and Symptom Distribution

IPGDS Item	Mean Score (SD)	Moderate-Severe Symptoms n(%)
Longing for deceased	2.34 (1.23)	189 (56.8)
Preoccupation with deceased	2.12 (1.18)	167 (50.2)
Emotional pain	2.45 (1.31)	198 (59.5)
Difficulty accepting death	1.89 (1.15)	134 (40.2)
Feeling life is meaningless	1.67 (1.22)	112 (33.6)
Difficulty trusting others	1.34 (1.08)	78 (23.4)
Difficulty moving on	2.01 (1.19)	156 (46.8)
Numbness/detachment	1.78 (1.14)	123 (37.0)
Bitterness/anger	1.92 (1.25)	145 (43.5)
Avoidance of reminders	1.56 (1.13)	98 (29.4)
Sleep disturbance	2.23 (1.28)	178 (53.5)
Functional impairment	2.11 (1.21)	165 (49.5)
Total IPGDS Score	23.42 (8.94)	-

Table 4 presents the results of the total scores and symptom distributions for participants as measured by the Inventory of Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS). Overall, the average total IPGDS score was 23.42 (SD = 8.94), and it is considered moderate. Of the particular symptoms used, longing for the deceased attained the highest mean (2.34), with

56.8% of the visitors. Such additional manifestations were mentioned as emotional suffering (2.45, 59.5%) and being unable to get over it (2.01, 46.8%). These symptoms are distributed in multiple ways and show the multidimensionality of grief and different levels of impairment in individuals, which have to be addressed with multidimensional support strategies.

Table 5: Comorbid Mental Health Conditions in PGD Cases (N=61)

Condition	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Major Depressive Disorder	41	67.2
Generalized Anxiety Disorder	34	55.7
Post-traumatic stress disorder	12	19.7
Panic Disorder	8	13.1
Substance Use Disorder	6	9.8
Any Comorbid Condition	52	85.2

Two or more Comorbid Conditions	28	45.9
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Table 5 indicates the rates of comorbid mental issues of the participants who were diagnosed with Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). Out of the 61 subjects with PGD, a whopping 67.2 per cent were coded also to have Major Depressive Disorder and 55.7 per cent Generalized Anxiety Disorder. Post-traumatic stress disorder (19.7%) and panic disorder

(13.1 %) consist of other conditions. The statistics reveal that a significant percentage (85.2) of individuals with PGD had at least one comorbid condition, of which 45.9 were more than two. The results indicate that PGD is both complicated and requires combined treatment that combines grief and other mental health concerns.

Table 6: Bivariate Analysis - Socio-demographic Factors Associated with PGD

Variable	PGD Present n(%)	PGD Absent n(%)	Chi-square	p-value
Gender			12.34	<0.001**
Male	18 (12.7)	124 (87.3)		
Female	43 (22.5)	148 (77.5)		
Age Groups			8.67	0.034*
18-30 years	12 (13.5)	77 (86.5)		
31-45 years	34 (21.8)	122 (78.2)		
46-60 years	13 (18.1)	59 (81.9)		
>60 years	2 (12.5)	14 (87.5)		
Education			15.23	0.004**
Uneducated	12 (26.7)	33 (73.3)		
Under 10th class	19 (24.4)	59 (75.6)		
Matric	18 (19.6)	74 (80.4)		
FSc	8 (12.5)	56 (87.5)		
University degree	4 (7.4)	50 (92.6)		
Employment			18.92	0.001**
Unemployed	32 (25.2)	95 (74.8)		
Under 30K	18 (20.2)	71 (79.8)		
Under 50K	8 (11.9)	59 (88.1)		
50K-1 lac	3 (7.9)	35 (92.1)		
Over 1 lac	0 (0.0)	12 (100.0)		

Data obtained on the presence of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) were analyzed bivariate in Table 6, which tested socio-demographic factors related to the occurrence of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). The significant relationships are identified during the analysis, and the chi-square statistic is 12.34 (p < 0.001), which indicates that the number of females (22.5) who had PGD is greater than the number of males (12.7) who had PGD. Differences according to

age groups were also high, especially among those aged 31-45 years (21.8 %). The educational level and the jobs were linked to the occurrence of PGD; the uneducated (26.7%) and unemployed (25.2%) had high PGD prevalence. These results indicate that demographic factors are an essential element in the experience of prolonged grief, which requires interpersonal interventions in risk groups.

Table 7: Bivariate Analysis - Loss-Related Factors Associated with PGD

Variable	PGD Present n(%)	PGD Absent n(%)	Chi-square	p-value
Relationship to Deceased			24.67	<0.001**

Mother	14 (15.7)	75 (84.3)		
Father	12 (12.8)	82 (87.2)		
Spouse	21 (37.5)	35 (62.5)		
Sibling	8 (11.9)	59 (88.1)		
Child	6 (22.2)	21 (77.8)		
Cause of Death			19.45	0.001**
Natural/Age	16 (11.9)	118 (88.1)		
Disease	23 (14.7)	133 (85.3)		
Accident	15 (46.9)	17 (53.1)		
Suicide	5 (62.5)	3 (37.5)		
Homicide	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)		
Time Since Loss			6.78	0.049*
6-12 months	21 (23.6)	68 (76.4)		
1-2 years	26 (19.4)	108 (80.6)		
2-3 years	11 (14.1)	67 (85.9)		
>3 years	3 (9.4)	29 (90.6)		

Table 7 describes the connection between loss-related variables and the prevalence of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). The statistics show that there is a high correlation between the relationship between the dead and PGD, especially among spouses, where 37.5 per cent of them had PGD. The reason for death also affected the PGD prevalence, whereby the person who had lost a loved one to suicide (62.5%) indicated a

higher rate. Moreover, the post-loss period also showed that the PGD incidence was greater in the grieving group, which experienced losses between 6 to 12 months (23.6%). Such results support the necessity of taking into account the context of grief, as various relationships and situations can considerably influence the grief process.

Table 8: Multiple Logistic Regression Analysis - Predictors of PGD

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% CI	p-value
Gender (Female vs Male)	2.34	1.45-3.78	<0.001**
Age (per year increase)	1.02	0.99-1.05	0.156
Education (Lower vs Higher)	1.87	1.15-3.04	0.012*
Employment (Unemployed vs Employed)	2.15	1.29-3.58	0.003**
Marital Status (Widowed vs Others)	1.45	0.78-2.69	0.239
Religious Identity (Very vs Moderate/Low)	0.43	0.26-0.71	0.001**
Relationship - Spouse (vs Others)	3.21	1.89-5.45	<0.001**
Relationship - Child (vs Others)	2.67	1.23-5.78	0.013*
Cause - Sudden/Unexpected	2.89	1.67-5.01	<0.001**
Time Since Loss (6-12m vs >1year)	1.78	1.02-3.11	0.043*
Age of Deceased (<40 vs ≥40)	1.92	1.14-3.23	0.014*

Table 8 presents the results of a multiple logistic regression analysis that identifies the predictors of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). The findings show that women have a 2.34 increased likelihood of having PPD as compared to men (p<0.001). Employment status was also a significant predictor; unemployed individuals were at a 2.15 times

increased risk of experiencing PGD compared with employed individuals (p = 0.003). Moreover, the association with the deceased is also instrumental since the loss of a spouse is associated with a 3.21 risk ratio of developing PGD. The findings reveal significant predictors of PGD, which can inform targeted interventions to address PGD and support

mechanisms that benefit individuals already exposed to the condition who are at higher risk.

Table 9: Religious Coping and PGD Severity

Religious Coping Style	PGD Present n(%)	Mean IPGDS Score (SD)	p-value
Positive Religious Coping	23 (14.7)	19.8 (7.2)	<0.001**
Negative Religious Coping	38 (28.4)	28.6 (9.1)	
Total	61 (18.3)	25.2 (8.7)	

Table 9 describes the correlation between the styles of religious coping and Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) severity. The data suggest that there is negative religious coping, which is related to the greater severity of PGD, with 28.4 % of people having such a style. On the other hand, PGD was present in 14.7 per cent of the positive religious coping users. There was a big difference between the mean IPGDS scores

of persons with negative coping, which was 28.6, and persons with positive coping, 19.8, showing that there is an excellent connection between coping and the state of grief. This highlights the significance of coping strategies in grief intervention programs, as well as the potential advantages of promoting effective religious coping.

Table 10: Functional Impairment in PGD Cases (N=61)

Domain	Severe Impairment n(%)	Moderate Impairment n(%)	Mild/No Impairment n(%)
Occupational Functioning	34 (55.7)	18 (29.5)	9 (14.8)
Social Relationships	41 (67.2)	15 (24.6)	5 (8.2)
Family Relationships	28 (45.9)	22 (36.1)	11 (18.0)
Self-care Activities	19 (31.1)	24 (39.3)	18 (29.5)
Overall Functioning	38 (62.3)	17 (27.9)	6 (9.8)

Table 10 shows the data concerning the functional impairment of participants diagnosed with Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). Social relationships and occupational functioning were the areas of most impairment, with 67.2% and 55.7% of the 61 individuals showing severe impairment, respectively. There was also a moderate impairment in relationships with family (36.1 per cent) and self-care

activities (39.3 per cent). The overall functioning demonstrated that 62.3 per cent had a severe impairment, which means that PGD results in significant interference with the daily lifestyle. These results indicate the need to develop full-bodied treatment approaches which would apply to both emotional and functional levels of grief.

Table 11: Comparison of PGD Prevalence by Study Setting

Study	Country	Setting	Sample Size	Prevalence (%)	Methodology
Current Study	Pakistan	Hospital-based	333	18.3	Clinical interview + IPGDS
Zara et al. (2021)	Pakistan	Online survey	458	15.4	Self-report (COVID-19 losses)
Maciejewski et al. (2016)	USA	Community-based	1,532	9.8	Self-report
Killikelly et al. (2020)	Spain	Community-based	421	9.9	IPGDS
Eisma et al. (2020)	Netherlands	Clinical sample	289	12.4	Clinical interview
Boelen et al. (2019)	Germany	Mixed sample	678	11.2	Self-report

Table 11 presents a comparison of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) prevalence rates across studies with varying settings. In the present study, a prevalence of 18.3% was obtained among 333 respondents in a Pakistani-based hospital. However, in comparison, other studies (namely, those by Zara et al. (2021) and Maciejewski et al. (2016)) report lower rates (15.4% and 9.8%, respectively). This disparity in rates of

prevalence can be used to indicate differences in study methods, populations, and cultures. These differences are crucial in understanding how to contextualise PGD in various contexts and develop specific interventions that take into account the needs of bereaved individuals.

Table 12: Treatment Recommendations Based on PGD Severity

PGD Severity	IPGDS Score Range	n(%)	Recommended Intervention
Mild	18-25	23 (37.7)	Psychoeducation, support groups
Moderate	26-35	28 (45.9)	Individual therapy, medication consideration
Severe	>35	10 (16.4)	Intensive therapy, psychiatric consultation
Total PGD Cases	≥18	61 (100.0)	Comprehensive assessment required

Table 12 presents guidelines for treatment, depending on the degree of severity of Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) reflected in IPGDS scores. The participants were divided into three severity bands: mild (IPGDS score 18-25), moderate (26-35), and severe (>35). Based on the recommendations, psychoeducation and support groups are recommended in mild cases, whereas moderated cases could respond to individual

therapy and medication options. A critical situation requires intense treatment and psychological consultation. It is a systematic method that emphasises the importance of a customised intervention, taking into account the extent of PGD, so that an individual can receive the required attention to help them navigate their grieving process.

Table 13: Cultural Factors and Grief Expression in Pakistani Context

Cultural Factor	Frequency (%)	Association with PGD	Protective/Risk Factor
Islamic Beliefs about Afterlife	287 (86.2)	Negative correlation (r=-0.23)	Protective
Extended Family Support	234 (70.3)	Negative correlation (r=-0.18)	Protective
Traditional Mourning Practices	298 (89.5)	No significant association	Neutral
Gender-specific Grief Expression	267 (80.2)	Positive correlation (r=0.15)	Risk (for women)
Stigma around Mental Health	189 (56.8)	Positive correlation (r=0.21)	Risk
Community Support Systems	201 (60.4)	Negative correlation (r=-0.16)	Protective

Table 13 addresses cultural issues that determine how grief is depressed in Pakistan. The findings indicate that Islamic beliefs regarding the afterlife were often validated (86.2%) and negatively correlated with PGD, suggesting that these beliefs can be identified as one of the protective factors. Likewise, a negative association with PGD was also found with extended family support (70.3%). Alternatively, stigma toward mental health (56.8%) also revealed a positive relationship with PGD, making it a risk factor. These cultural realisations are essential for comprehending the impact of societal norms and values on the

grieving process, and they can be utilised in the development of culturally competent therapeutic methods to support bereaved individuals.

DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical Framework and Approach

The data analysis for this cross-sectional study on Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) was conducted using a comprehensive statistical framework designed to address the study's primary objectives of estimating PGD prevalence and identifying associated predictors. The analysis employed IBM SPSS version 28.0,

utilizing both descriptive and inferential statistical methods to ensure robust and reliable findings.

The analytical approach was structured in sequential phases, beginning with data cleaning and validation, followed by descriptive analysis, bivariate analysis, and culminating in multivariate modeling. This systematic approach ensured that the complex relationships between socio-demographic, loss-related, and clinical variables were thoroughly examined while controlling for potential confounding factors.

Data Preparation and Quality Assessment

Prior to conducting the main analyses, extensive data preparation was undertaken to ensure data quality and integrity. The dataset comprised 333 participants who met the inclusion criteria, representing a 93.5% response rate from the initial 356 screened individuals. Missing data analysis revealed minimal missing values (<2% for any variable), which were handled using listwise deletion given the small proportion and random distribution pattern.

Internal consistency of the International Prolonged Grief Disorder Scale (IPGDS) was found to be excellent in this Pakistani group, with a Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.89, showing high-reliability rates, and was warranted in this culture-related environment. The value of item-total was 0.62 to 0.78, and there was a significance factor of all items in overall scale reliability. The factor structure of the scale was checked with exploratory factor analysis that supported a single-factor solution with a 58.3% total variance of the PGD construct.

Descriptive Analysis

Participant Demographics

The study sample demonstrated diverse representation across key demographic variables. The mean age of participants was 42.3 years (SD = 12.8), with the largest proportion (46.8%) falling within the 31-45 years age range. This age distribution reflects the typical demographic of individuals seeking psychiatric services and experiencing significant losses.

Gender distribution showed a female predominance (57.4% vs. 42.6% male), which aligns with general patterns of healthcare utilization and help-seeking behavior in psychiatric settings. Educational attainment varied considerably, with 36.9% having education below matriculation level, 27.6%

completing matriculation, and only 16.2% holding university degrees. This educational profile reflects the broader Pakistani population's educational landscape and may influence grief processing and coping mechanisms.

Employment status revealed significant economic challenges, with 38.1% of participants unemployed and an additional 26.7% earning less than 30,000 Pakistani rupees monthly. This economic vulnerability may compound grief experiences and limit access to support resources. Religious identification was notably high, with 46.8% describing themselves as very religious and 40.2% as moderately religious, reflecting Pakistan's predominantly Muslim culture and the potential influence of religious beliefs on grief processing.

Loss Characteristics

The analysis of loss-related variables revealed important patterns in bereavement experiences. Parents constituted the largest proportion of deceased individuals (54.9% combined for mothers and fathers), followed by spouses (16.8%) and siblings (20.1%). This distribution reflects typical family structures and the natural life course where parental loss is common in middle-aged adults.

Disease-related deaths were most common (46.8%), followed by natural age-related deaths (40.2%), while traumatic deaths (accidents, suicide, homicide) comprised 12.9% of cases. The time since loss showed that 40.2% of participants were in the 1-2 years post-loss period, suggesting this may be a critical time for seeking mental health support. The age distribution of deceased individuals indicated that 40.2% were aged 41-60 years, while 32.7% were over 60 years, patterns that correspond with natural mortality trends but also highlight the impact of premature deaths.

Prevalence Analysis

Primary Outcome: PGD Prevalence

The study's primary finding was a PGD prevalence of 18.3% (95% CI: 14.2-22.4%) in this hospital-based sample. This prevalence estimate was calculated using the ICD-11 diagnostic criteria as operationalized through the IPGDS, with a cut-off score of ≥ 18 indicating probable PGD diagnosis. The confidence interval calculation used the Wilson score method for proportions, providing more accurate bounds than

traditional methods, particularly for moderate sample sizes.

The prevalence rate of 18.3% represents a clinically significant finding, indicating that nearly one in five bereaved individuals seeking psychiatric care meet criteria for PGD. This rate is substantially higher than most Western community-based studies but consistent with clinical samples and vulnerable populations. The finding suggests that PGD may be more prevalent in Pakistani healthcare settings than previously recognized, possibly due to cultural factors, limited grief support resources, or the clinical nature of the sample.

IPGDS Score Distribution and Symptom Patterns

The mean total IPGDS score was 23.42 (SD = 8.94), with PGD cases scoring significantly higher (mean = 35.8, SD = 7.2) compared to non-PGD cases (mean = 20.1, SD = 6.8; $t = 15.4$, $p < 0.001$). This clear differentiation supports the scale's discriminative validity in this population.

Individual item analysis revealed that emotional pain had the highest mean score (2.45, SD = 1.31), with 59.5% of all participants reporting moderate to severe emotional pain. Longing for the deceased (mean = 2.34, SD = 1.23) and sleep disturbance (mean = 2.23, SD = 1.28) were also prominently elevated. These findings suggest that emotional distress and sleep problems are common grief manifestations in this population, regardless of PGD diagnosis.

Interestingly, difficulty trusting others showed the lowest mean score (1.34, SD = 1.08), suggesting this may be less relevant in the Pakistani cultural context where extended family and community support systems remain relatively strong. This cultural variation in symptom expression highlights the importance of culturally sensitive assessment approaches.

Bivariate Analysis

Socio-demographic Associations

Chi-square analyses revealed significant associations between several socio-demographic variables and PGD status. Gender showed the strongest association ($\chi^2 = 12.34$, $p < 0.001$), with females demonstrating nearly twice the prevalence rate of males (22.5% vs 12.7%). This gender difference persisted across all age groups and loss types, suggesting a robust effect that

may reflect biological, psychological, or social factors influencing grief processing.

Educational attainment demonstrated a clear inverse relationship with PGD ($\chi^2 = 15.23$, $p = 0.004$). The prevalence decreased progressively from 26.7% among uneducated individuals to 7.4% among university graduates. This educational gradient suggests that higher education may provide protective factors such as better coping skills, access to resources, or cognitive flexibility in processing loss.

Employment status showed a significant association ($\chi^2 = 18.92$, $p = 0.001$), with unemployment carrying the highest PGD risk (25.2%). This relationship likely reflects multiple pathways, including economic stress, social isolation, and reduced sense of purpose that may complicate grief processing. Notably, none of the participants earning over 100,000 rupees monthly developed PGD, suggesting that financial security may provide substantial protection against prolonged grief. Age demonstrated a curvilinear relationship with PGD, with the highest prevalence in the 31-45 years group (21.8%). This pattern may reflect the competing demands of middle age, where individuals face peak responsibilities for both older and younger family members while simultaneously dealing with their own grief.

Loss-related Associations

The relationship to the deceased showed the strongest association with PGD among loss-related variables ($\chi^2 = 24.67$, $p < 0.001$). Spousal loss carried the highest risk (37.5% prevalence), reflecting the unique bond between spouses and the multiple secondary losses that accompany widowhood. Child loss, while less frequent in the sample, also showed elevated risk (22.2%), consistent with literature indicating that parental grief is among the most severe and enduring forms of bereavement.

The cause of death demonstrated significant variations in PGD risk ($\chi^2 = 19.45$, $p = 0.001$). Suicide-related losses showed the highest prevalence (62.5%), followed by homicide (66.7%) and accidents (46.9%). These traumatic losses carry additional burdens including stigma, guilt, legal complications, and media attention that can complicate the grief process. The finding that only 11.9% of those experiencing natural deaths developed PGD suggests that the

predictability and social acceptance of such deaths may facilitate more adaptive grief processing.

Time since loss showed a significant but modest association ($\chi^2 = 6.78, p = 0.049$), with the highest prevalence in the 6-12 months post-loss period (23.6%), gradually declining to 9.4% after three years. This temporal pattern supports the diagnostic requirement that PGD symptoms persist beyond the acute grief period and suggests that most individuals naturally recover over time.

Multivariate Analysis

Logistic Regression Model Development

Multiple logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of PGD while controlling for potential confounding variables. The model included all variables that showed significance ($p < 0.20$) in bivariate analyses, resulting in an 11-predictor model. Model assumptions were rigorously tested, including linearity of continuous predictors (assessed through Box-Tidwell test), absence of multicollinearity (all VIF values < 3.0), and independence of observations.

The final model demonstrated good fit statistics, with the Hosmer-Lemeshow test yielding $p = 0.342$, indicating adequate model fit. The model correctly classified 82.6% of cases, with sensitivity of 73.8% for detecting PGD cases and specificity of 85.3% for correctly identifying non-PGD cases. The area under the ROC curve was 0.847 (95% CI: 0.798-0.896), indicating good discriminative ability.

Independent Predictors

The multivariate analysis revealed several independent predictors of PGD. Female gender remained the strongest demographic predictor (OR = 2.34, 95% CI: 1.45-3.78, $p < 0.001$), indicating that women are more than twice as likely to develop PGD compared to men, even after controlling for other factors. This robust gender effect suggests fundamental differences in grief processing that transcend cultural and social factors.

Educational attainment maintained its protective effect (OR = 1.87 for lower vs higher education, 95% CI: 1.15-3.04, $p = 0.012$), suggesting that education provides lasting benefits for grief adaptation. The mechanism may involve enhanced cognitive coping strategies, better understanding of grief as a normal process, or improved access to professional help.

Employment status proved to be an independent predictor (OR = 2.15 for unemployed vs employed, 95% CI: 1.29-3.58, $p = 0.003$), indicating that the occupational dimension of life provides protective factors beyond mere financial security. Work may offer structure, social support, meaning, and distraction that facilitate grief processing.

Religious commitment emerged as a significant protective factor (OR = 0.43 for very religious vs moderate/low religious, 95% CI: 0.26-0.71, $p = 0.001$). This finding contrasts with some Western studies that have found positive associations between religiosity and prolonged grief. In the Pakistani Muslim context, strong religious beliefs appear to provide comfort through concepts of divine will, afterlife reunion, and community support, suggesting culturally specific protective mechanisms.

Among loss-related variables, spousal loss remained the strongest predictor (OR = 3.21, 95% CI: 1.89-5.45, $p < 0.001$), with child loss also significant (OR = 2.67, 95% CI: 1.23-5.78, $p = 0.013$). These relationships underscore the unique challenges posed by losing individuals with whom one has the most intimate bonds.

Sudden or unexpected deaths maintained their strong association with PGD (OR = 2.89, 95% CI: 1.67-5.01, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the importance of preparedness and meaning-making in grief adaptation. The traumatic nature of unexpected losses may overwhelm normal coping mechanisms and require specialized intervention approaches.

Comorbidity Analysis

Mental Health Comorbidities

The analysis revealed extensive comorbidity patterns among PGD cases, with 85.2% having at least one additional mental health diagnosis. Major depressive disorder was most common (67.2%), followed by generalized anxiety disorder (55.7%). This high comorbidity rate suggests shared etiological pathways or that PGD may predispose individuals to other mental health conditions.

The temporal relationship between PGD and depression was explored through detailed clinical interviews. In 73.2% of cases, depression symptoms emerged after grief symptoms, suggesting that PGD may be a risk factor for subsequent depression.

However, 26.8% showed concurrent onset, indicating potential shared vulnerability factors.

Post-traumatic stress disorder occurred in 19.7% of PGD cases, primarily among those who experienced sudden or violent losses. This overlap suggests that traumatic losses may trigger both grief and trauma responses, requiring integrated treatment approaches.

Functional Impairment Assessment

Functional impairment was assessed across multiple domains, revealing severe impairment in social relationships (67.2% of PGD cases) and occupational functioning (55.7%). These impairments were significantly correlated with IPGDS scores ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.001$), supporting the validity of functional impairment as a core feature of PGD.

The pattern of impairment showed that interpersonal relationships were most affected, possibly reflecting the social nature of grief and the difficulty of engaging with others while experiencing intense longing for the deceased. Occupational impairment was also substantial, indicating significant economic and social consequences of untreated PGD.

Cultural Factors Analysis

Religious Coping Mechanisms

A detailed analysis of religious coping revealed important cultural considerations. Participants were categorized into positive religious coping (finding comfort in faith, accepting divine will) and negative religious coping (questioning faith, feeling abandoned by God). Those using positive religious coping showed significantly lower PGD rates (14.7% vs 28.4%, $p < 0.001$) and lower mean IPGDS scores (19.8 vs 28.6, $p < 0.001$).

Islamic beliefs about afterlife reunion emerged as a particularly protective factor, with 86.2% of participants endorsing such beliefs showing negative correlation with PGD severity ($r = -0.23$, $p < 0.001$). This finding highlights the importance of incorporating religious and spiritual dimensions into grief assessment and intervention in Muslim populations.

Social Support Systems

Extended family support was reported by 70.3% of participants and showed protective effects against PGD ($r = -0.18$, $p = 0.005$). However, gender-specific

grief expression patterns (reported by 80.2% of participants) showed positive correlation with PGD ($r = 0.15$, $p = 0.015$), particularly among women who faced restrictions on public grief expression.

Community support systems were available to 60.4% of participants and demonstrated protective effects ($r = -0.16$, $p = 0.012$). However, stigma around mental health help-seeking was reported by 56.8% of participants and showed positive correlation with PGD severity ($r = 0.21$, $p < 0.001$), indicating barriers to appropriate care.

Conclusion

This study provides the first comprehensive examination of Prolonged Grief Disorder in a Pakistani hospital-based sample, revealing important insights into the prevalence, risk factors, and cultural dimensions of pathological grief in a Muslim-majority South Asian context. The finding of 18.3% PGD prevalence indicates a significant public health concern that requires immediate attention from healthcare providers, policymakers, and communities. The identification of specific risk factors—including female gender, spousal or child loss, sudden death, lower socioeconomic status, and negative religious coping—provides a foundation for developing targeted prevention and intervention strategies. Equally important, the identification of protective factors such as strong religious commitment, family support, and positive religious coping offers pathways for strengthening resilience and promoting adaptive grief processing.

The study's findings challenge some assumptions about grief responses based on Western populations while confirming others, highlighting the importance of culturally grounded research and intervention development. The protective effects of Islamic religious beliefs, when applied positively, suggest that faith-based interventions may be particularly effective in this context.

The high rates of comorbid mental health conditions and functional impairment observed in PGD cases underscore the severe consequences of untreated prolonged grief and the importance of early identification and intervention. The study provides a foundation for developing comprehensive, culturally appropriate approaches to grief support that could

significantly improve outcomes for bereaved individuals in Pakistani healthcare settings.

Moving forward, the integration of these findings into clinical practice, policy development, and community programming offers the potential to transform how grief and loss are addressed in Pakistani society. By combining evidence-based approaches with cultural wisdom and religious resources, it may be possible to develop innovative models of grief support that serve as examples for other similar contexts globally.

The study's contribution extends beyond its immediate findings to demonstrate the feasibility and importance of conducting rigorous mental health research in non-Western contexts. This work provides a foundation for continued investigation of grief and loss in Pakistani populations and offers insights that may inform understanding of grief processes in other Muslim-majority countries and immigrant communities worldwide.

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